

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

SYMMETRIC LIPSCHITZ FUNCTIONS

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ABSTRACT

We investigate Lipschitz symmetric functions on a Banach space X with a symmetric basis. We consider power symmetric polynomials on R or l_1 and show that they are Lipschitz on the unbounded subset of consisting of vectors on R or l_1 such that $|x_n| \leq 1$.

Keywords: symmetric functions, Lipschitz function, Lipschitz constant.

Introduction

Symmetric functions of infinitely many variables play an important role in the nonlinear functional analysis and its applications [1].

Let X be a real Banach space. We recall that a Schauder basis e_n in X is symmetric if it is equivalent to the basis $e_{\sigma(n)}$ for every permutation σ of the set of positive integers N .

A function $f: X \rightarrow R$ is called symmetric if $F(\sigma(x)) = f(x)$ for all $x \in X$. It is naturally to study symmetric polynomials and analytic functions X as simple nonlinear symmetric functions. Algebras of symmetric analytic functions and their generalizations on real and

complex Banach spaces were investigated by many authors (see [2-6]). However, some Banach spaces like c_0 do not support symmetric polynomials while support a lot of symmetric Lipschitz functions. In [1] proposed symmetric slice polynomials for approximation of uniformly continuous symmetric functions on S_{c_0} . But the slice polynomials are not Lipschitz in the general case. In this paper we consider some classes of Lipschitz symmetric functions on a real Banach space X with a symmetric basis.

1 Symmetric Lipschitz functions on finite spaces.

Theorem 1. *Symmetric function $F_p(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p$, $F_p: R^n \rightarrow R$ is Lipschitz with a constant $L_{F_p} \leq p$ for all $|x_i| < 1, i = 1, \dots, n$.*

Proof. Let $F_p(x) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p$, $F_p(y) = \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^p$ are symmetric functions which satisfy the condition of the theorem.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(F_p(x); F_p(y)) &= |F_p(x) - F_p(y)| = \left| \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p - \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^p \right| = \left| \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i^p - y_i^p) \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i^p - y_i^p| = \sum_{i=1}^n |(x_i - y_i)(x_i^{p-1} + x_i^{p-2}y_i + \dots + x_i y_i^{p-2} + y_i^{p-1})|. \end{aligned}$$

Since $|x_i| < 1$ and $|y_i| < 1$ then

$$\rho(F_p(x); F_p(y)) \leq \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i| p = p \rho(x; y).$$

Therefore $F_p(x)$ is a symmetric Lipschitz function with a constant $L_{F_p} \leq p$.

Theorem 2. *Symmetric function $(F_1(x))^k = (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^k$, $F_1^k: R^n \rightarrow R$ is Lipschitz with a constant $L_{F_1^k} \leq kn^{k-1}$ for all $|x_i| < 1, i = 1, \dots, n$.*

Proof. Functions $(F_1(x))^k = (\sum_{i=1}^n x_i)^k$, $(F_1(y))^k = (\sum_{i=1}^n y_i)^k$ are symmetric and $|x_i| < 1, |y_i| < 1, i = 1, \dots, n$.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho((F_1(x))^k; (F_1(y))^k) &= |(F_1(x))^k - (F_1(y))^k| \\ &= |F_1(x) - F_1(y)| \left| F_1^{k-1}(x) + F_1^{k-2}(x)F_1(y) + \dots + F_1(x)F_1^{k-2}(y) + F_1^{k-1}(y) \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i| \left| \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{k-1} + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right)^{k-2} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i \right)^{k-2} + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i \right)^{k-1} \right|. \end{aligned}$$

Every $x, y \in R^n$ satisfy the condition $|x_i| < 1$ and $|y_i| < 1$ then

$$\rho\left(\left(F_n(x)\right)^k; \left(F_n(y)\right)^k\right) \leq kn^{k-1} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i| = kn^{k-1} \rho(x; y).$$

Therefore $\left(F_1(x)\right)^k$ is a symmetric Lipschitz function with a constant $L_{F_1^k} \leq kn^{k-1}$

Theorem 3. Symmetric function $\left(F_p(x)\right)^k = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p\right)^k$, $F_p^k: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is Lipschitz with a constant $L_{F_p^k} \leq pkn^{k-1}$ for all $|x_i| < 1, i = 1, \dots, n$.

Proof. Functions $\left(F_p(x)\right)^k = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p\right)^k$, $\left(F_p(y)\right)^k = \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i^p\right)^k$ are symmetric and $|x_i| < 1, |y_i| < 1, i = 1, \dots, n$.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho\left(\left(F_p(x)\right)^k; \left(F_p(y)\right)^k\right) &= \left| \left(F_p(x)\right)^k - \left(F_p(y)\right)^k \right| \\ &= \left| F_p(x) - F_p(y) \right| \left| F_p^{k-1}(x) + F_p^{k-2}(x)F_p(y) + \dots + F_p(x)F_p^{k-2}(y) + F_p^{k-1}(y) \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i^p - y_i^p| \left| \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p\right)^{k-1} + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p\right)^{k-2} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^p + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^p \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i^p\right)^{k-2} + \left(\sum_{i=1}^n y_i^p\right)^{k-1} \right|. \end{aligned}$$

Since $|x_i| < 1$ and $|y_i| < 1$ then

$$\begin{aligned} \rho\left(\left(F_p(x)\right)^k; \left(F_p(y)\right)^k\right) &\leq kn^{k-1} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i^p - y_i^p| \\ &= kn^{k-1} \sum_{i=1}^n |(x_i - y_i)(x_i^{p-1} + x_i^{p-2}y_i + \dots + x_i y_i^{p-2} + y_i^{p-1})| \leq pkn^{k-1} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i| \\ &= pkn^{k-1} \rho(x; y). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\left(F_p(x)\right)^k$ is a symmetric Lipschitz function with a constant $L_{F_p^k} \leq pkn^{k-1}$

Theorem 4. Symmetric function $G_2(x) = \sum_{i,j=1}^n x_i x_j$, $G_2: \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is Lipschitz with a constant $G_2 = n - 1$ for all $|x_m| < 1, m = 1, \dots, n$.

Proof. Functions $G_2(x) = \sum_{i,j=1}^n x_i x_j$, $G_2(y) = \sum_{i,j=1}^n y_i y_j$ are symmetric and $|x_m| < 1, |y_m| < 1, m = 1, \dots, n$.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(G_2(x), G_2(y)) &= \left| \sum_{i,j=1}^n x_i x_j - \sum_{i,j=1}^n y_i y_j \right| \\ &= |x_1 x_2 + x_1 x_3 + \dots + x_1 x_n + \dots + x_{n-1} x_n - (y_1 y_2 + y_1 y_3 + \dots + y_1 y_n + \dots + y_{n-1} y_n)| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2} |x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 + \dots + x_1^2 + x_n^2 + \dots + x_{n-1}^2 + x_n^2 - y_1^2 - y_2^2 - y_3^2 - \dots - y_1^2 - y_n^2 - \dots - y_{n-1}^2 - y_n^2| \\ &\leq \frac{n-1}{2} |x_1^2 - y_1^2 + x_2^2 - y_2^2 + \dots + x_n^2 - y_n^2| \leq \frac{n-1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i^2 - y_i^2| = \frac{n-1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i| |x_i + y_i| \end{aligned}$$

Since $|x_i| < 1$ and $|y_i| < 1$ then

$$\rho(G_2(x), G_2(y)) \leq (n-1) \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i - y_i| = (n-1) \rho(x; y).$$

Therefore G_2 is a symmetric Lipschitz function with a constant $L_{G_2} \leq n - 1$

2 Symmetric Lipschitz functions on infinite spaces.

Theorem 5. Symmetric function $F_p(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x_i^p$, $F_p: l_1 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is Lipschitz with a constant $L_{F_p} \leq p$ for all $|x_i| < 1, i = 1, \dots, n$.

Proof. Let $F_p(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x_i^p$, $F_p(y) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} y_i^p$ are symmetric functions which satisfy the condition of the theorem.

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(F_p(x); F_p(y)) &= |F_p(x) - F_p(y)| = \left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x_i^p - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} y_i^p \right| = \left| \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x_i^p - y_i^p \right| \\ &\leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |x_i^p - y_i^p| = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |(x_i - y_i)(x_i^{p-1} + x_i^{p-2}y_i + \dots + x_i y_i^{p-2} + y_i^{p-1})|. \end{aligned}$$

Since $|x_i| < 1$ and $|y_i| < 1$ then

$$\rho(F_p(x); F_p(y)) \leq \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |x_i - y_i| p = p \rho(x; y).$$

Therefore $F_p(x)$ is a symmetric Lipschitz function with a constant $L_{F_p} \leq p$.

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